

Cognitive Aspects of North Indian Music: How Children Learn to Compose and Improvise in an Oral Tradition

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ABSTRACT

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This study explores how children learn to compose and improvise North Indian classical music focussing on the styles of *kḥayāl*, *ṭhumrī* and *dhrupad*. It explains the contexts in which North Indian classical music is learnt in contemporary India, interrogates the concepts of improvisation and composition and reviews research into the development of cognitive processes necessary to achieve fluency in performance. Following a review of the literature, video data from lessons/*tālīm* collected during a period of fieldwork is thematically analysed, focussing on the teaching and learning strategies used at various stages in the learning process. The theoretical perspective of the study is interpretivist and underpinned by a social constructivist epistemology. Within the literature there are many accounts that emphasise the ways in which the *guru-śiṣya paramparā* encourages the memorisation and improvisation of key phrases of a *rāg* through the intensive internalisation of a *guru's* style. In contrast to this, group lessons in institutions tend to have a dual focus on classificatory knowledge and learning to perform many *rāgs* from memory, usually without the same degree of focus on improvisation. The observations reveal that imitation is the most prevalent strategy used with students at all levels in *both guru-śiṣya paramparā* and music school contexts. There is very little spontaneous improvisation by students, and memorisation is key to the development of advanced students' ability to reproduce and recombine the complex phrases sung by their teachers with a high degree of speed and accuracy. The material sung by the teacher (which is often improvised for the specific teaching context and students) exemplifies the improvisational processes in real time, incorporating aspects of formulaic and idiomatic construction. It is these skills demonstrated by experienced teachers that support the development of students' abilities to apply formulas and improvise in performance settings.